

A New Approach for the Voltage Stability in a Multibus System Using Ann Technique

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ABSTRACT

Voltage instability is a state of power system encountering a deplorable voltage level. This paper describes the expressions of Line Quality Factor (LQF) and Fast Voltage Stability Index (FVSI), which may be measured as sign of voltage collapse under inhibited condition of an interconnected power system. Artificial Neural Network Technique has been useful to recognize the voltage collapse condition. The newness of this method is that, once the ANN model of the system is built-up, through on line checking of the load of the weak bus, the present method can immediately calculate the FVSI and LQF without going through the complex classical calculations. The developed ANN technique has been experienced in IEEE 30 bus test system and is established to be in excellent agreement with the result obtained by standard method.

Key words: voltage stability, ANN, bus, LQF, FVSI.

1. INTRODUCTION

The nonstop increase in demand for electric power has resulted in an ever more complex interrelated system, forced to operate closer to the limit of stability. Voltage instability is characterized by the inability of the system to retain its voltage near the nominal value, even with a change in joined susceptance at the load bus. In a multibus interconnected system, if load (active and/or reactive) increases incessantly the voltage of each bus decreases. From this condition, different voltage stability limits may be obtained. Researches are going for long to study voltage instability of an interconnected power system [1],[2],[3]. A review of literature reveals that, researchers have been trying to investigate the static aspect of load flow solutions by applying various methods for identifications of the point of split and to estimate the stability margin of the system.[4],[5],[6]. ANNs have paying attention the great deal of consideration because of their pattern recognition capability and their capability to handle corrupted data. They have been successfully applied in certain power engineering problems. [7],[8]. ANN has the ability to solve the problems with high non-linearity such as system security and stability assessment. [9],[10]. An ANN is programmed, by presenting it with a training set of input-output patterns from which, it learns the relationship between them. Its ability to perform is well affected by the chosen training data as well as network topology and training scheme.

This paper focuses on two different methods of stability indices. Computer simulation has been conducted to calculate the stability indices on IEEE 30 bus test system considering different loading conditions after detecting the degree of weakness of load buses. The proposed ANN model is then trained to correlate the voltage stability status of the system with changing load pattern. A comparison of the results obtained by ANN model with classical calculation, has been presented in the text to point out the efficiency of ANN based technique in predicting of voltage collapse condition.

2. MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS

An interconnected system is reduced to a single line network and applied to assess the overall system stability. Utilizing the same concept but using it for each line of the network stability criteria can be developed. Consider a single line of an interconnected network shown in Fig. 1. The line is connected to other lines